

Angelo Leogrande^{1*o^}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^University of Bari Aldo Moro

Companies producing machinery and equipment in OECD countries

They decreased on average by 15.64% between 2005 and 2022 for the OECD countries considered

The OECD calculates the number of companies producing machinery and equipment. The data refers to the period between 2005 and 2022.

Machinery and equipment manufacturing companies in OECD countries in 2022. Italy led the ranking with an impressive number of 18,163 companies, followed by Germany with 16,056 companies. This dominance of Italy and Germany underlines the central role that these two countries play in the machinery manufacturing sector within the OECD. Poland and Spain registered 6,100 and 5,599 companies respectively, highlighting the significant presence of these countries in the European equipment industry. The Czech Republic with 4,589 companies and France with 4,163 also contributed substantially to the continent's production panorama. In the Netherlands, the number of manufacturing companies was 3,517, ranking just below France. Hungary and Sweden had 2,271 and 2,185 businesses respectively, demonstrating a robust manufacturing sector in these countries. Greece and Denmark, with 1,859 and 1,835 companies respectively, showed notable industrial activity despite the smaller size of their markets compared to those of major European producers. Slovakia and Finland recorded similar numbers, with 1,805 and 1,538 businesses respectively, followed closely by Portugal with 1,527 and Austria with 1,426. Switzerland, known for its precision and quality in production, had 1,375 companies active in the sector. Belgium and Romania showed similar figures, with 1,216 and 1,211 companies, highlighting a moderate but significant presence in the sector. Serbia counted 1,042 enterprises, followed by Bulgaria with 928 enterprises, reflecting the growing importance of these countries in the Balkans in the context of industrial production. Norway and Slovenia had 800 and 730 companies respectively, while Croatia registered 716 companies active in the machinery and equipment manufacturing sector. Israel, a country known for its technological innovations, counted 545 enterprises, showing remarkable production capacity despite its relatively small size. In the Baltics, Estonia registered 222 companies, Lithuania 205 and Latvia 182, underlining the presence of a smaller but still relevant manufacturing sector in the region. North Macedonia had 152 businesses, just above Bosnia and Herzegovina with 151. Among the countries with the fewest businesses, Costa Rica had 107 businesses, followed by Cyprus with 55, Malta with 33 and Luxembourg with 24 businesses. These numbers reflect the wide variability in industrial capacities and production sector sizes across different OECD member countries. Overall, these data highlight the diversity and distribution of machinery and equipment manufacturing companies across OECD countries. The higher concentration in countries such as Italy and Germany highlights the dominant role of these nations in the sector, while the significant presence in countries such as Poland,

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Spain and the Czech Republic indicates a broader and more competitive distribution of industrial production across Europe.

Machinery and equipment manufacturing firms in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022. Over the period between 2005 and 2022, machinery and equipment manufacturing firms in OECD countries showed significant changes in both absolute numbers and percentages. Analyzing the data, a diversity of trends emerges between the various countries, reflecting different economic and industrial dynamics. In Austria, the number of businesses decreased from 1,641 to 1,426, marking an absolute loss of 215 businesses, equivalent to a decrease of 13.10%. This decline could be attributable to various factors, including the relocation of production or a restructuring of the sector in response to technological and market changes. Costa Rica recorded a notable increase, with companies going from 68 to 107, with an absolute increase of 39 units, equal to 57.35%. This significant increase could be the result of favorable economic policies, foreign direct investment and a development of the local manufacturing sector. Czechia saw a substantial decline in the number of businesses, from 6,232 to 4,589, with a loss of 1,643 businesses, corresponding to a decrease of 26.36%. This decline could be linked to a combination of factors, including post-EU accession economic restructuring and international competition. Estonia recorded an increase in the number of companies, from 143 to 222, with an increase of 79 units, equal to 55.24%. This result likely reflects an expanding business environment and policies supporting innovation and industry. Hungary suffered a drastic reduction in the number of businesses, from 5,433 to 2,271, with a loss of 3,162 units, corresponding to a decline of 58.20%. This significant decline could be attributed to a number of factors, including changes in industrial policy and shifts in global supply chains. Latvia showed notable growth, with businesses increasing from 111 to 182, marking an increase of 71 units, or 63.96%. This increase may be due to improved economic conditions and opportunities in the manufacturing sector. Lithuania also saw an increase, although more modest, with a transition from 169 to 205 companies, an increase of 36 units, equal to 21.30%. This figure reflects growth in the industrial sector, perhaps supported by investments and development policies. Poland recorded a notable increase in the number of companies, going from 4,195 to 6,100, an increase of 1,905 units, equal to 45.41%. This significant increase could be the result of strong economic development and growing production capacity. In Portugal, the number of businesses decreased from 2,039 to 1,527, with a loss of 512 units, equivalent to a decline of 25.11%. This decline could be linked to internal economic factors, including structural problems and competitiveness. Slovenia saw a slight decline in the number of businesses, from 800 to 730, with a loss of 70 units, or 8.75%. This decline could reflect a stabilization of the industrial sector after a period of growth or changes in market dynamics. Bulgaria recorded a decrease in the number of companies, from 979 to 928, with a loss of 51 units, equal to 5.21%. This slight decline could be indicative of stabilization or specific economic challenges. Finally, Romania saw a reduction in the number of companies, from 1,304 to 1,211, with a loss of 93 units, equal to 7.13%. This decline could be linked to changes in economic policies or industrial challenges. In summary, the data show varied dynamics of machinery and equipment manufacturing firms in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022. Some countries, such as Costa Rica, Latvia, and Poland, experienced significant growth, likely reflecting favorable economic conditions and investments in the sector. Others, such as Hungary and Czechia, have seen substantial declines, perhaps due to economic restructuring, international competition and relocation.

Conclusion. The number of companies producing machinery and equipment decreased by 15.64% between 2005 and 2022 for the OECD countries considered. However, there are countries that have seen the number of machinery and equipment manufacturing companies grow, namely Latvia with +63.96%, Costa Rica with +57.35% and Estonia with 55.24%. Among the countries that have had

significant reductions in the number of machinery and equipment manufacturing companies are Portugal with -25.11%, the Czech Republic with -26.36%, and Hungary with -58.20% . Considering 2022, it appears that more than 50% of machinery and equipment manufacturing companies are located in Italy - 22.06%, Germany with 19.50%, Poland with 7.41%, and Spain with 6.80%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Number of Enterprises in Administrative and Support Service Activities (2022)

Percentage Change in Number of Enterprises in Administrative and Support Service Activities (2005-2022)

